

nuclei per hyphal cell; similar response of in vitro growth to temperature (see table); and disease development on maize inbred Cuba 257.

Responses of rice (R₆) and maize isolates (R₁) to carbendazim, benodanil, and thiabendazole were also similar. Two isolates, however, responded differently to thiophanate-M, dichloroline, and aureofungin. The rice isolate was more sensitive to dichloroline and less to thiophanate-M than the maize isolate, which failed to grow at the lowest thiophanate-M concentration (35 µg ai/ml). □

Comparison of maize and rice isolates of *R. solani* f. sp. *sasakii*, New Delhi, India.

Isolate	Origin	Nuclei/hyphal cell		Mode nuclear no.	Growth rate (mm/24 h)		Disease developed ^a on maize inbred Cuba 257 at			Mean virulence on 7 hosts ^c
		Range	Mean		25°C	30°C	25°C	30°C	35°C ^b	
R ₁	Maize	4-8	6.6	6	47	45	2.0	3.5	+ ^d	2.6
R ₂	Maize	3-13	6.6	6	37	37	1.5	1.5	+	2.0
R ₃	Maize	3-11	6.3	6	46	47	2.0	2.0	+ ^d	2.6
R ₄	Maize	3-13	6.3	6	27	35	2.0	3.5	+ ^d	2.9
R ₅	Rice	3-16	7.0	6	46	44	1.0	2.0	+	2.5
R ₆	Rice	3-9	5.4	6	47	47	3.0	3.0	+	2.7

^aDisease recorded on maize inbred Cuba 257 on 1-5 scale. ^b+ = growth in traces. ^cAverage of 4 readings each on 7 hosts. ^d production of infection cushions.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization INSECT RESISTANCE

Rice varietal reaction to leafroller (LF) and yellow stem borer (YSB)

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We evaluated 6 promising 120- to 140-d rices for reaction to LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* and YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* in an adaptive research trial at Thozhudur, Thanjavur District, in 1983 thaladi when there was severe insect pressure.

Ten plants from nonreplicated plots of each variety were randomly chosen for scoring. LF reaction was based on the number of affected leaves in relation to the total leaves. YSB was scored based on the number of deadhearts as related to tillers/plant. Scoring was at flowering in Nov.

LF incidence ranged from 2 to 12%. Co 44, Pusa 169, AD9408, and Co 43 had resistant reaction. All varieties but Co 44 had fewer than 20% deadhearts, indicating YSB resistance (see table). □

Rice varietal reaction to LF and YSB incidence, Thozhudur, India.

Variety	Infestation (%)	
	LF ^a	YSB ^b
IET6262 (Pankaj/Vijaya)	11	11
AD9408 (IR20/IR8)	3	15
BS8 (IR36/Co 13)	12	8
Co 43 (Dasal/IR20)	8	18
Co 44 (ASD5/IR20)	2	23
Pusa 169 (IR28/P140)	2	19

^aBased on number of affected leaves in relation to total leaves. ^bBased on number of deadhearts as related to tillers/plant.

Rice resistance to brown planthopper (BPH) in the Solomon Islands

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About two and one-half annual irrigated rice crops are grown under mechanized cultivation on the Guadalcanal Plains of the Solomon Islands. The local BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål population is highly virulent and resistant varieties only last 1-3 yr. We continually screen varieties for BPH resistance.

BG379-5 (BG96-3/Ptb 33) is believed to possess the Ptb 33 resistance gene and was first screened for BPH resistance in the 1980 International Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery. It was highly resistant,

Yield and resistance of BG379-5 to pests^a on the Guadalcanal Plains, Solomon Islands.

Seeded	Harvested	Resistance ^b to			Yield (t/ha)	Remarks
		BPH	LR	ShB		
29 Jul 83	28 Nov 83	1.5	1.0	4.0	7.3	Heavy ShB incidence
11 Aug	12 Dec	1.0	1.0	—	4.6	Stunted and yellowing
20 Oct	16 Feb 84	2.0	1.0	2	3.8	Moderate army worm damage
29 Oct	5 Mar	1.4	1.0	3	5.3	—
26 Nov	28 Mar	1.4	1.0	—	6.2	Moderate brown spot incidence
17 Dec	18 Apr	3.0	1.5	5.3	4.8	Heavy army worm attack
20 Jan 84	18 May	4.5	1.0	2	5.0	—
10 Feb	7 Jun	7.3	1.0	—	4.0	60% hopperburned
19 Mar	16 Jul	7.0	1.0	—	4.9	—
6 Apr	21 Jul	6.0	1.0	—	3.4	—

^a LR = leafroller, ShB = sheath blight. ^bRated according to the *Standard evaluation system for rice*: 1 = most resistant, 9 = most susceptible.

scoring 1 on the 1-9 IRRI *Standard evaluation system for rice* and yielded 7-8 t/ha. It was released for commercial use on the Solomon Islands in 1982 and until recently has shown BPH resistance.

To monitor BG379-5 performance, we conducted yield trials from Jul 1973 to Jul 1984. Seeds were planted monthly in randomly chosen 3- × 5-m plots with 4 replications. Thirty, 40, and 40 kg N/ha